

PUBLIC PERCEPTION IN THE MANAGEMENT OF INTEGRATED ISLAMIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN TOJO UNA-UNA REGENCY

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Abstract: This research aims to describe; (1) What is the community's perception of the implementation of curriculum management (2) What is the community's perception of the implementation of school and community relations management at SD IT AL-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una. This research uses mixed research methods with an exploratory type of research. Data collection techniques through observation, distribution of questionnaires, interviews and documentation studies. The data analysis process was carried out using descriptive percentage analysis techniques. The research results show that: (1) community perception of curriculum implementation at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una with a percentage of 85.85% is in the good category. This can be seen in the implementation of curriculum management functions in planning, implementation and also the evaluation process. By combining the national curriculum and the Wahdah Islamiyah curriculum, this school is much sought after by the public. (2) Community perception of the implementation of school and community relations management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una with a percentage of 88.17% is in the good category. This can be seen in the planning, implementation and evaluation of the management of school and community relations which has been carried out well, so that through these public relations activities SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una is increasingly known to the community.

Keywords: *Community perception, implementation of curriculum management, implementation of school and community relations management.*

Introduction

Educational development and all the dimensions within it are quite interesting issues to be studied, scrutinized, discussed and analyzed critically so that the implementation of education in Indonesia can be understood fundamentally, comprehensively, realistically, evenly and objectively.

In order to develop and improve the quality of education, the government has established eight National Education Standards (SNP) as stated in Article 35 paragraph (1) of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System which is further explained in Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 Regarding National Education

Standards, namely: content standards, process standards, graduate competency standards, teacher and education staff standards, facility and infrastructure standards, management standards, financing standards, and education assessment standards. National education standards, as stated above, are essentially the direction and goal of education implementation. (Redaksi Grafika, 2011).

Currently, public awareness regarding the urgency of education is increasing, which can be seen from the increasing enthusiasm of parents to entrust their sons and daughters to superior and quality educational institutions. This parental tendency has a strong reason, so that their children become human beings who can be useful for their national and religious communities. So parents play an important role in providing direction and policies regarding the education of their sons and daughters.

According to Azyumardi Azra (1998), there is a current trend for Muslim communities to provide superior Islamic educational institutions. In fact, they are at the forefront as centers for the development and empowerment of religious (Islamic) education in various aspects (Azra & Thaha, 2012).

Integrated Islamic educational institutions are expected to be able to be a solution to bridge the concerns of some middle class Muslim communities who dream of the existence of Islamic educational institutions that are able to provide broad and in-depth religious values education to their students, and also make their students capable of mastering various sciences and technologies (Nata, 2001).

The idea of establishing an Integrated Islamic School is expected to be able to integrate general education and religious education in a balanced manner, by accommodating all the wishes and hopes of Muslim parents. Muhaimin even emphasized that the Integrated Islamic School was born from the desire to integrate general knowledge and religion, thereby producing graduates who not only master various sciences and technologies but also have faith, piety and noble character (Muhaimin et al., 2012).

The cost of education at SDIT is relatively expensive, but parents' interest in sending their children to SDIT remains high. According to one of the student guardians at SDIT Alam Al-Karim Bandar Lampung, they don't care what the costs are because of the parents' obsession with the success of their children's education. The logic behind their thinking is that if a child wants to be smart, they have to find a good school, and good schools are expensive. This opinion will of course influence the social level of those who are prestige oriented. As stated by Agus Maimun and Agus Zaenul Fitri, the choice of educational institution is based on at least two things, namely social status and

religion (Maimun & Fitri, 2010).

According to Forster and Fenwick (2015), the implementation of good and planned Islamic education management will have a very important influence in forming a number of Islamic values consistently for all elements of teaching and education staff, including principals, teachers, employees and students in an educational institution. The Islamic values in question include aspects of honesty, transparency, kinship, helping others, self-development, respect and cooperation. Success in implementing Islamic values in an educational institution depends on how individuals make decisions to actively follow religious values and accept or reject these values as part of the structure for building character as a Muslim.

Islamic schools with integrated accessories are new arrivals in the history of Islamic education in Indonesia. Even though it is relatively new, this Islamic school with an integrated slogan shows a good existence, and is currently a trend for some Muslim communities, especially in urban areas, even though the costs are quite expensive. According to Suyatno, in a relatively short time, the number of integrated Islamic schools has reached \pm 10,000 schools throughout Indonesia. (Suyatno, 2013: 361).

If we examine further the history of Islamic education in Indonesia, we will find ideas and ideas about the concept of Islamic education with an integrated model, although not with an integrated label. A school education system that combines general and religious studies has existed before. In 1909, Abdullah Ahmad founded the Adabiyah School in West Sumatra, although initially this school was in the form of a Madrasah, but in the end it turned into a school, HIS. The curriculum concept is the same as the current Integrated Islamic School concept, namely integration (Ramayulis : 2012: 302).

Management of school and community relations is a network of interactions planned by the school so that it can be accepted in the community and gain aspirations and sympathy from the community. The definition of relations with society according to Abdurrachman is an activity to instill and obtain understanding, good will, trust, respect from the public, a body in particular and society in general (Suryosubroto, 2004).

The school can provide information to the community, so that the community forms its own opinion about the school. From a review of the interests of society, it can be said that society can benefit from and absorb the results of thought and developments in technological knowledge that are useful for society itself (Mulyono, 2008, hlm. 209).

The community (parents) have a very important role in helping to make school programs a success and have the right to have an opinion, but still

comply with the provisions set by the school. The role of the community is not just in the form of proposals or suggestions, the community can also create a management structure so that school programs can be well established so that they can be useful for the progress of the school. Regarding educational principles, the school is still obliged to implement them (Syifa Nurfajriah, et al, 2021).

In Tojo Una-Una Regency, an integrated Islamic elementary school was established in 2019 under the auspices of the Tojo Una-Una Regency Youth and Sports Education Service and managed by the Wahdah Islamiyah Education Foundation (YPWI) Tojo Una-Una Regency. This school was established based on the idea of the board of the Wahdah Islamiyah Education Foundation (YPWI) who wanted an educational institution in Tojo Una-Una Regency that combined the national curriculum and the unique Wahdah Islamiyah curriculum.

Wahdah Islamiyah's unique curriculum consists of reading and writing lessons and memorizing the Al-Qur'an (BTHQ), Arabic, Hadith and tarbiyah (instilling the concepts of aqidah and adab). Students have completed reading the Al-Qur'an with a target of 2 juz, namely juz 29 and juz 30 with the application of tajwid knowledge. And also several programs for parents to study and deepen the Koran, such as parent studies and the dirosa program.

The public's enthusiasm for the existence of the Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una Integrated Islamic Elementary School is increasing, this can be seen from the increasing number of interested people entering each new school year. SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una has also been recorded in the Basic Education Data (DAPODIK) since 2021 and currently has six study groups with a total of 130 students since it was founded in 2019.

According to Burhanuddin (2003), there are seven educational management substances, namely (1) curriculum or learning, (2) student affairs, (3) human resources, (4) facilities and infrastructure, (5) finance, and (6) public relations, and (7) special services. Initial observations carried out, researchers found that the SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una Curriculum is quite unique, namely different from other elementary schools, and the role of the SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una public relations team is also no less important for building community trust so that SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una can be known by the community through social media, promotions between peers, as well as social sharing activity programs with the community carried out together with the foundation.

In the research with the title "Community Perceptions in the Management of Integrated Islamic Elementary Schools in Tojo Una-Una Regency" the author only discusses two of the seven educational management

substances above, namely curriculum management and management of school and community relations which researchers find interesting to study at SD IT Al - Wahdah Tojo Una-Una.

Method

This research was conducted at the Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una IT Elementary School which is located on Jalan Tanjumbulu, Sumoli Village, Ratolindo District, Tojo Una-Una Regency, Central Sulawesi. This research uses mixed research methods, namely a combination of methods. qualitative research and quantitative research methods. The type of research used in this research is descriptive explanatory research. This research describes how the community perceives the management of the Integrated Islamic Primary School in Tojo Una-Una Regency. All data collected through questionnaires was analyzed using descriptive percentage analysis techniques.

In this research, primary data was taken directly from informants, namely parents of students, the general public, and school principals and teachers as supporting informants in this research. The research subjects in this study were parents/guardians of students and the general public around the SD IT Al-wahdah Tojo Una-Una school, totaling 55 people. In this research, researchers used three data collection techniques, namely observation, distribution of questionnaires, interviews and documentation.

The questionnaire used in this research is a closed questionnaire where the answers are provided so that respondents just have to choose, with a direct questionnaire using a graded scale. The graded scale in this questionnaire uses a modified Likert scale with 4 answer choices, namely, Always (SL) with a score of 4, Often (SR) with a score of 3, Sometimes (KK) with a score of 2, Never (TP) with a score of 1. The questionnaire in this research was given to parents of students and the community, to describe the community's perception of the management of the Al-Wahdah Integrated Islamic Elementary School in Tojo Una-Una Regency. Distribute questionnaires or questionnaires using Google Forms. In this research the data obtained from respondents will be analyzed by using descriptive analysis with percentage techniques, which formulated as follows:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100\%$$

Where:

P = Percentage of answers

f = Frequency of values obtained from all items

n = Number of respondents

100% = Fixed Number

To calculate the percentage in the score, the following formula is used:

$$P = \frac{Sc}{Si} \times 100\%$$

Where:

P = Percentage of research results

Sc = Score obtained from all informants

Si = Maximum score that must be achieved.

100% = Fixed number

The scores obtained for each indicator will then be classified as follows:

Table: Classification Criteria

No	Percentage Range (%)	Qualification
1.	91%-100%	Very good
2.	81%-90%	Good
3.	71%-80%	Pretty good
4.	61%-70%	Not good
5.	Kurang dari 60%	Very Not Good

Source: (Thoha: 1990:89)

Result

The variable in this research is how the community perceives the management of the AL-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una Integrated Islamic Elementary School. The data from this research is in the form of a percentage score obtained from data from distributing questionnaires to 55 respondents who are parents/guardians of students and the community in the Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una Integrated Islamic Elementary School environment which is divided into several indicators, namely: 1) implementation of curriculum management, 2) Implementation of school and community relations management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una.

1. Implementation of Curriculum Management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una

Based on the indicators above, the implementation of curriculum management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una is divided into 16 statements, namely: 1) In planning the school curriculum, SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una involves the school committee and parents of students, 2) Curriculum planning SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una refers to the national goals of education, 3) The SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una curriculum is prepared based on the national curriculum which is combined with the typical school curriculum wahdah islamiyah, 4) Implementation of the curriculum at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una is adjusted to the school's vision and mission, 5) Implementation of the SD

IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una curriculum based on the educational calendar, 6) During the implementation of learning, the school teaches all general subjects in accordance with the national curriculum integrated with the typical subjects of the Wahdah Islamiyah curriculum, 7) During learning, for general subjects, the teacher inserts several relevant verses of the Qu'an and hadith according to the topic learning, 8) The school implements Islamic activities by getting used to sunnah prayers, congregational prayers, wearing Islamic clothing and maintaining relationships with people of the opposite sex, 9) The school carries out mandatory extracurricular activities as well as optional extracurricular, 10) The school gives students the freedom to choose the extracurricular program they are interested in. 11) the school curriculum is socialized to parents and guardians of students, 12) Evaluation of curriculum implementation at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una is carried out every 6 months, 13) Assessment of student learning outcomes is carried out through mid-semester programs, semester exams and daily tests, 14) The learning program created by the school is in accordance with the school's vision and mission. 15) Character education development has an impact on children's character both inside and outside school.

The results of data processing on the Implementation of curriculum management variable which is divided into three sub-indicators, namely planning, implementation and evaluation of the curriculum, can be seen in the summary table of curriculum management indicators as follows:

No.	Sub Indicator	Actual Score	Ideal Score	Presentage(%)	Criteria
1.	Curriculum planning	596	880	67,72	Good
2.	Curriculum implementation	2.023	2.200	91,95	Good
3.	Curriculum evaluation	403	440	91,59	Good
Average		1.007,3	1.173,3	85,85	Good

Thus, it can be concluded through the presentation of the summary table that the percentage of curriculum management indicators at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una is in the good category seen from the average percentage above, namely 85.85%.

2. Public Relations Management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una

The implementation of public relations management at SD IT Al-Wahdah

Tojo Una-Una is divided into 14 statements as follows: 1) The school forms a special team to handle school public relations, 2) the school publishes the school profile, 3) the school publishes school activities on its social media account owned, 4) SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una's social media is quite helpful in providing information needed by the community, 5) SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo public relations programs Una-Una is socialized to parents, guardians and the community, 6) SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una often participates in community social activities, 7) The school has programs that involve parents, foundations and the community, 8) the school holds regular meetings every 6 months with the school committee, 9) the school establishes collaboration with local government agencies, 10) SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una actively participates in activities organized by the local education office, 11) the school publishes student achievements on social media as a strategy school branding, 12) teachers conduct home visits to solve student problems, 13) Schools involve certain community figures in various appropriate school activities and programs.

The results of data processing on the Implementation of school and community relations management variable which is divided into three sub-indicators, namely planning, implementation and evaluation of public relations programs can be seen in the indicator summary table as follows:

No.	Sub Indicator	Actual Score	Ideal Score	Presentage(%)	Criteria
1.	Perencanaan program humas	182	220	82,72	Good
2.	Pelaksanaan program humas	2.144	2.420	88,6	Good
3.	Evaluasi Program Humas	196	220	89	Good
Average		840,6	953,3	88,17	Good

Thus, it can be concluded through the presentation of the summary table that the percentage of public relations management indicators at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una is in the good category seen from the average percentage above, namely 88.17%.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research results, it shows that the public's perception of the implementation of curriculum management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una with a percentage of 85.85% is included in the good category. This shows

that the school principal has carried out and implemented the school curriculum well. This can be seen in the planning, implementation and evaluation activities of the curriculum which have been carried out well.

Based on the results of interviews with the principal and several informants and also supported by school documents, curriculum planning at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una still refers to the national goals of education, this is in accordance with what is stated in the national education system law number 20 of the year 2003 article 3 which reads: national education functions to develop abilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to educate the nation's life, aiming to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty. unity, noble character, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and a democratic and responsible citizen” (Depdiknas, 2003:9).

Curriculum planning is an activity that systematically prepares a series of learning activities at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una for one academic year in two semesters. The learning content in the curriculum for each subject is outlined in the competencies that must be mastered by students in accordance with the learning load stated in the curriculum structure. The competencies in question consist of competency standards and basic competencies which are developed based on graduate competency standards.

In planning the SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una curriculum, it refers to national educational goals and also educational goals in accordance with the school's vision, mission and goals. The mission is a description of the goals that will be achieved within a certain period of time and is used as the main school program.

Curriculum planning at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una is prepared based on the national curriculum, namely the K13 curriculum and the independent curriculum and combined with the typical Islamic Wahdah school curriculum. The content of the curriculum material at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una is divided into subject group A and subject B. Subject group A, consists of general subjects namely mathematics, Indonesian, arts and culture, civics education, PJOK, crafts and IPAS. Subject group B consists of diniyah subjects, namely BTHQ (Reading and Writing and Memorizing the Al-Qur'an), PAI, Arabic and tarbiyah. Meanwhile, local content is a typical school subject consisting of self-development and extracurricular activities.

In preparing the curriculum at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una, the principal and the curriculum team that was formed were involved, and the principal was responsible for managing the school curriculum. Supporting factors in curriculum planning at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una consist of

internal factors and external factors, internal factors including teachers and the curriculum team, external factors namely supervisors, school consultants and parents of students. In planning the school curriculum, it tries to highlight the uniqueness of the school, especially in aspects of religious knowledge such as memorizing the Al-Qur'an and memorizing short hadiths which are generally not applied in other schools.

Implementation of ideal curriculum management results from careful planning. A curriculum that has been developed will not become a reality if it is not implemented, in this case it is not actually used in schools and classes. In principle, this implementation integrates philosophical aspects of the curriculum, objectives, subject matter, and strategies for teaching and learning activities as well as curriculum evaluation (Mahmud dkk,)

Researchers found that the implementation of the SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una curriculum was based on the national education calendar of the Education and Culture Service of Tojo Una-Una Regency, because SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una was under the auspices of the Education and Youth Service of Tojo Una-Una Regency. In carrying out or carrying out learning, teachers include Islamic values in the learning process, by integrating verses from the Koran and hadith that are relevant to the learning topic being taught, as well as dressing in sharia and maintaining relationships with members of the opposite sex.

The school also carries out Islamic activities as a form of habituation for students, such as memorizing and reciting short hadiths during morning assembly, carrying out dhuha prayers in congregation, and muraja'ah dhikr and daily prayers after performing dhuha prayers, after Entering midday time, students are directed to perform midday prayers together, these habituation activities do not only apply to students, teachers and staff are also directed to be involved in these activities. These habits are carried out to shape students' religious character.

This is also in accordance with the results of research at SD IT in Bandar Lampung, which explains that the reason they send their sons and daughters to this school is, among other things, because they want to send their children to a school that not only has quality general education but also provides in-depth religious education, not only limited to theory but also practice in everyday life (Nurasiah & Isnaeni Ahmad, 2018).

As a result of an interview with the student's parents, he said that he enrolled his child in SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una so that his child could memorize the Al-Qur'an and get a more in-depth religious education and also excel in general subjects.

Meanwhile, the school also carries out self-development activities in the form of extracurricular activities, both mandatory and optional extracurricular activities, mandatory extracurricular activities such as scouts, optional extracurricular activities such as taekwondo, and Islamic talent development which consists of developing recitations, tartil, sirah nabawiyah. Students are given the freedom to choose what extracurricular activities they are interested in.

The results of the interview with the school principal said that the students of SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una were also quite capable of competing in the various competition activities held, this could be seen from the various achievements of the students in the field of taekwondo who had won several times at the national level. As well as the competitions held at the Al-Wahdah IT Elementary School district level also achieved quite a lot of achievements.

At the beginning of every semester, the Wahdah Islamiyah Education Foundation always holds regular meetings with student guardians and parents to socialize the curriculum and programs that will be implemented by the school. This aims to ensure that parents also know about the programs carried out by the school so they can work together in educating participants education both at school and at home.

In carrying out evaluations of teacher performance in implementing the learning curriculum, it is carried out by holding regular meetings at the beginning of every month. The purpose of this regular meeting is to evaluate the course of the learning process, and to socialize the weekly programs that will be carried out, coordination between class teachers, general subject teachers and special Wahdah Islamiyah subject teachers.

Meanwhile, to assess student learning outcomes, this is done in the classroom by assessing attitudinal competency and knowledge competency. Apart from that, the school also assesses student learning outcomes at each mid-semester and end of semester. In carrying out an evaluation of the implementation of the curriculum at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una there are also several obstacles that usually occur, namely the sub-optimal implementation of the curriculum, in this case one of which is due to several teachers moving to another school.

This is also in line with what Hasan expressed in (Rusman, 2018) that there are several factors that influence curriculum implementation, namely, implementation strategies, assessment characteristics, teacher knowledge about the curriculum, attitudes towards the curriculum and directing skills.

From the discussion above, the author can conclude that the

implementation of curriculum management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una has been carried out well. Public interest is starting to increase in SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una because of its unique curriculum as well as habitual worship activities and the target of graduates memorizing at least 2 JUZ of the Al-Qur'an which is not implemented in state schools or other madrasah schools.

2. Implementation of School Public Relations Management

Based on the research results, it shows that the community's perception of the implementation of school and community relations management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una with a percentage of 88.17% is included in the good category. This shows that the school principal has carried out and implemented the school and community relations management curriculum well. This can be seen in the planning, implementation and evaluation of school and community relations which have been carried out well.

Based on the results of interviews with the school principal and several informants, also supported by school documents, the researcher found that, at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una a special team to handle school public relations activities had not yet been formed, so the implementation of public relations programs was still handled by the school principal, in the field of administration and teachers, there is no clear structure or composition of the public relations implementation team.

Furthermore, schools also publish school profiles, by posting school nomenclature, publishing learning activities via social media. SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una has social media accounts such as Facebook, Instagram and YouTube. It is hoped that the content uploaded via the school's social media accounts will be able to provide information and also provide an overview of learning activities at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una to the wider community.

The existence of social media is also very helpful for branding schools among the community, based on the results of presentations from several informants that they get information about SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una from social media such as Facebook, and often see video and photo posts from students who have completed their memorization targets or congratulations for students who have completed their memorization targets. And they are interested in enrolling their children in SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una.

SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una also often participates in community social activities and collaborates with one of the zakat institutions, namely Gerai WIZ Tojo Una-Una, in various social activities, such as ifthar stocking activities held in the month of Ramadhan, stocking activities qurban which is carried out after the Eid al-Adha holiday, and activities to share basic necessities and also

activities to care for Palestine, the community around the school also feels the benefits of social programs which is held.

Meanwhile, researchers also found that at Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una IT Elementary School, they were also actively involved in activities organized by the Dikpora education service, such as participating in o2SN activities, Ministry of Religion activities such as PAI Stage activities and winning 3 level runners-up. province and other activities. SD IT Al-Wahdah also collaborates with the nearest Community Health Center to control the health of students and carry out various infectious disease prevention programs.

SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una also often conducts home visits to obtain information if there are students who have problems or need more guidance and to find out more about the students' conditions regarding their internal conditions such as the condition of their parents, learning facilities at home, relationships with members. family, and the commitment of parents and other family members in the development of students which influences the condition of students at school, this aims to be a form of collaboration between teachers and parents to build effective communication between teachers and parents. Researchers also found that teachers were also very responsive to input or problems that occurred among students.

Based on the results of the discussion above, the author concludes that the implementation of school and community relationship management has been carried out well. Building school and community relations is very important to foster community trust. The school uses social media to introduce SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una so that it is better known to the public.

Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that

The public's perception of the implementation of curriculum management at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo with a percentage of 85.85% is in the good category. This can be seen from the implementation of management functions such as planning, implementation and also the curriculum evaluation process, and community perceptions regarding the implementation of management of school and community relations at SD IT Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una with a percentage of 88.17% in the good category. This can be seen in the implementation of school and community relations management which has been carried out starting from planning, implementation and evaluation activities. With a unique curriculum and appropriate management strategies for school and community relations, the Al-Wahdah Tojo Una-Una IT Elementary school has received a good reception among the community with the number of interested parties increasing every year.

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